

The Role of Comorbid Conditions in Exacerbating Mortality Risk Among Patients with Diabetes Mellitus During the COVID-19 Pandemic

RUZIMURODOV Nodir, ARIPOVA Tamara, MUSAKHODJAYEVA Diloram,

AZIZOVA Zukhra

Institute of Immunology and Human Genomics, Tashkent, Uzbekistan,

Corresponding author: Ruzimurodov Nodir Fazliddinovich, ruzimurodov.2019@mail.ru

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5194-1113>

Keywords: Diabetes Mellitus, COVID-19, Comorbid Conditions, Mortality Risk, Systemic Inflammation.

Introduction: The COVID-19 pandemic has posed significant challenges to global healthcare systems, particularly for individuals with pre-existing health conditions. Among these, diabetes mellitus (DM) is one of the most critical factors associated with severe COVID-19 outcomes. The pathophysiological mechanisms linking diabetes and COVID-19 involve chronic hyperglycemia, which impairs immune response, increases systemic inflammation, and leads to endothelial dysfunction. Diabetic patients are more susceptible to infections due to poor glycemic control, and this vulnerability is exacerbated by common comorbidities such as hypertension, obesity, chronic lung diseases, and chronic kidney disease.

Hypertension, often present in diabetic patients, contributes to endothelial dysfunction and increases the risk of thrombosis and cardiovascular complications, particularly when compounded by COVID-19-induced inflammatory responses. Obesity, a frequent companion of diabetes, exacerbates the inflammatory burden through adipose tissue-driven cytokine release, impairing both immune function and metabolic control. Chronic lung disease and chronic kidney disease further compound the risk of adverse COVID-19 outcomes, as these conditions reduce organ function and heighten susceptibility to respiratory and renal failure, respectively.

Given the complex interplay between diabetes, comorbidities, and COVID-19, it is critical to understand the role of these factors in determining patient outcomes during the pandemic. Furthermore, the protective effects of vaccination on mitigating the impact of comorbidities and improving prognosis in diabetic patients remain essential for clinical practice.

Objective: To assess the impact of various comorbid conditions on the risk of mortality in patients with diabetes mellitus during the COVID-19 pandemic and evaluate the mitigating effects of vaccination on disease progression and outcomes.

Materials and Methods: The study was conducted on a cohort of 300 patients with diabetes mellitus who were treated for COVID-19 during the pandemic. Participants were categorized into three groups based on their vaccination status and diabetes history:

- Group 1: Patients with pre-existing type 2 diabetes before contracting COVID-19.
- Group 2: Patients who developed type 2 diabetes after COVID-19 and were vaccinated.
- Group 3: Patients who developed type 2 diabetes after COVID-19 but were not vaccinated.

Inclusion criteria included confirmed diagnoses of type 2 diabetes and COVID-19, along with comorbidities such as hypertension, obesity, chronic lung diseases, and chronic kidney disease. Clinical data were collected, including blood pressure (for hypertension), BMI (for obesity), respiratory function tests (FEV1 for lung disease), serum creatinine levels, GFR (for kidney function), and liver function (ALT, AST for gastrointestinal comorbidities). Vaccination details and COVID-19 severity were also documented. Statistical analysis was used to compare the prevalence and severity of comorbid conditions across the groups and evaluate the effects of vaccination on patient outcomes.

Results: Hypertension was prevalent across all groups, with a higher incidence in unvaccinated patients (Group 3). Systolic blood pressure averaged 145 mmHg (± 15) in Group 3, compared to 135 mmHg (± 12) in Group 2, indicating better blood pressure control in vaccinated individuals. Obesity was another significant factor, with 65% of Group 3 exhibiting BMI values consistent with obesity (average BMI 32.5 kg/m² ± 3.5), while vaccinated patients (Group 2) showed lower obesity levels (average BMI 30.2 kg/m² ± 3.0).

Chronic lung disease (CLD) was present in 30% of unvaccinated patients, who had poorer respiratory function (average FEV1 60% ± 10). Vaccinated patients showed better respiratory outcomes, with FEV1 averaging 70% ± 8 . Chronic kidney disease (CKD) also worsened in unvaccinated patients, with creatinine levels averaging 120 mmol/l (± 20) and GFR dropping to 45 ml/min/1.73 m² (± 10), while vaccinated individuals exhibited better kidney function with lower creatinine levels and higher GFR.

Vaccination significantly reduced the risk of severe COVID-19 complications, including diabetic neuropathy, retinopathy, and mortality. Unvaccinated patients had a higher mortality rate compared to vaccinated individuals, underscoring the protective role of vaccination in reducing systemic inflammation and improving metabolic and organ function.

Conclusion: Comorbid conditions such as hypertension, obesity, chronic lung disease, and chronic kidney disease significantly increase mortality risk in diabetic patients

during the COVID-19 pandemic, particularly among unvaccinated individuals. The presence of these comorbidities exacerbates the inflammatory and metabolic disturbances caused by COVID-19, leading to poorer outcomes and higher rates of complications. However, vaccination plays a crucial role in mitigating these effects by reducing systemic inflammation, improving metabolic control, and enhancing organ function. These findings highlight the importance of vaccination and comprehensive management of comorbid conditions to improve outcomes in diabetic patients during the pandemic.